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WOMANBEING IN NIGERIAN LITERATURE

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Abstract

The ideological debate on the roles and representations of women in Nigerian literature or, more appropriately, the war on gender, is still raging, particularly in the Nigerian literary and intellectual space. The general argument of feminist writers and critics in Nigeria is that the whole feminine history has been man-made. Even ‘history’ as a word and discipline is becoming heavily contested since, in the opinion of the radical feminists, it is simply ‘**his story**’, hence an urgent need for ‘**her story**’ which would explore the exploits of the feminine gender. For this reason, charges of paternalism, misogyny and male chauvinism are frequently raised against {male} writers, especially by radical feminists. Anchored on the theoretical postulations of gender studies, the contention in this research is that the quick and radical conclusions about the “improper” representations of women is often done hastily and without a thorough analysis and comprehension of texts and contexts both at the macro and micro level. The prevalent argument herein is that the representation of women in Nigerian literature is much more balanced and complex than is often recognized; and that the relationship between men and women is not exactly that of master and slave in most Nigerian literary texts. Thus, this investigation focuses attention on the enviable roles of women, and the implications of womanbeing in some Nigerian literary texts to show that the ‘norm’ of misrepresentation of women is not always the case in male-authored, Nigerian texts – as radical feminists would have us believe.

Key Words: Womanbeing, Feminism, Nigerian literature, African culture, Literary criticism,

Introduction

Perhaps, it seems appropriate to begin with a brief note on the term “womanbeing”, which happens to be the subject of the title of this research. The term can be traced beyond Chukwuma Azuonye’s “Power, Marginality and Womanbeing in Igbo Oral Narratives”, a paper presented at a public lecture at the Livingston College, Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey, New Brunswick, U.S.A., on April 20, 1992. According to Azuonye, the expression was coined by the organisers of the 17th annual conference of African Literature Association held in New Orleans in March 1991, which had as its theme: “Nwanyibu: Womanbeing in African Literature.” The word proved attractive to the current investigation, especially as it seems to capture the entire essence of being of the feminine folk.

Allegations of Misrepresentation of Womanbeing in Nigerian Literature

Prior to the publication of *Anthills of the Savannah*, Chinua Achebe was a recipient of fierce accusations of misrepresentations of women as well as denying them a voice, particularly in his published narrative, *Things Fall Apart*, a text which was making great waves at the time for its realistic portrayal of the African cultural space. Radical feminists like Chukwuma Helen, Molaria Ogundipe-Leslie and the likes have vehemently written articles and books against perceived male chauvinism and female subjugation. In her “The Face of Eve: Feminist Writing in African Literature”, Chukwuma Helen makes the following hefty allegation in defence of feminism:

{Men wrote} about themselves, their wives, homes, their ideals, aspirations and conflicts, their confrontation with the white man and his ways, in sum their society at large. They were the masters and traditionally accepted mouthpieces of their women folk. (101)

One of the glaring accusations above is that while men wrote about themselves and their exploits, they had the full backing of tradition. In other words, that the misrepresentation of womanbeing is sanctioned by the cultural society. As this work progresses, we shall interrogate the allegation to ascertain its truthfulness or otherwise as well as to show whether the allegation is an unintended outworking of the influence of Western education.

Chukwuma Helen is not alone in this finger-pointing allegation. Igbokwe Chima in her “The Portrayal of Women in African Literature: Reflections on Alkali’s *The Stillborn* and *The Virtuous Woman*” agrees with Chukwuma, for she writes that:

In the novels of Elechi Amadi, the female characters are allowed to remain only at the fringes of cultural, social and economic activities. She is made to submit to male superiority. Madume in Elechi Amadi’s *The Concubine* is embittered and disappointed by the fact that his wife gave birth to only female children. In the works of Cyprian Ekwensi such as *Jagua Nana...* the female protagonists are pushed out of urban cultural relevance by being portrayed as women of easy virtue at the beck and call of amorous successful males... Okonkwo beats up Ojiugo and consequently breaks the week of peace in *Things Fall Apart*. Ekwueme in Elechi Amadi’s *The Concubine*, tries to unleash physical disciplinary measures on Ahuruole.

(83)

Another angle from which Igbokwe’s accusation aligns with that of Chukwuma Helen above is that both scholars agree that while the men occupy the front burner in the narration of their exploits and subjugations of women, they had the support of the Nigerian culture. However, in Igbokwe’s

reference to Okonkwo in Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, no mention at all is made of the fact that Okonkwo is heavily sanctioned by the same culture for breaking the Week of Peace.

On the surface, this accusation may look flowery and credible, especially given that feminism now amplifies allegations of female subjugations. However, in the same *Things Fall Apart*, when one contemplates on the characterization of the sacred role of Chielo both as priestess and prophetess of Agbala, one begins to wonder if she is female as well as a character in Achebe's literary text, which is often used as a benchmark for the criticism against his representation of women. Although she features in very limited scenes and is often regarded as one of the minor characters in the text, Chielo serves as a powerful mediator between the gods and the people (including males), her gender notwithstanding. Even Okonkwo, who is characterized as fearless and having no regard whatsoever for women, does not dare her spiritual powers or questions it. His sheer masculinity loses its erection before Chielo's commanding presence, and he does nothing but respects it. Of the encounter between Chielo and Okonkwo in *Things Fall Apart*, the narrative voice tells us thusly:

{Chielo} had now reached Okonkwo's compound and was talking with him outside his hut. She was saying again and again that Agbala wanted to see his daughter, Ezinma. Okonkwo pleaded with her to come back in the morning because Ezinma was now asleep. But Chielo ignored what he was trying to say and went on shouting that Agbala wanted to see his daughter. Her voice was as clear as metal, and Okonkwo's women and children heard from their huts all that she said. Okonkwo was still pleading that the girl had been ill of late and was asleep. Ekwefi quickly took her to their bedroom and placed her on their high bamboo bed.

The priestess suddenly screamed. ‘Beware, Okonkwo!’ she warned.
‘Beware of exchanging words with Agbala....’ (70-71)

It is worthy to note that Chielo in the above encounter wields the power of her influence without uttering too many words in response to Okonkwo’s suggestion. The authority of her physical presence is enough to tame Okonkwo’s idiosyncratic tendencies. As we see in the text, all that he does is merely to voice persistent pleadings and throws them at Chielo’s indifferent ears.

Happily, mention needs to be made that not all African female writers believe that all African literary narratives project womanbeing negatively. Here, for instance, is Flora Nwapa, a powerful voice in African creative and critical writing, voicing an opinion somewhat different from that of the bandwagon. In her “Women and Creative Writing in Africa”, she goes ahead to mention specific names and texts in which the ‘norm’ of negative portrayal of women is not the case:

How do African literary texts project women? A few of them have tried to project an objective image of women, an image that actually reflects the reality of women’s role in the society. Peter Abraham’s *A Wreath for Udoma* and Sembene Ousmane’s *God’s Bits of Wood* recognize the ‘the full and complete woman’ and provide role models for the female relationship... All three women are portrayed, not as victims of male subjugation in a patriarchal society, but as full woman-beings who take up their rightful positions in the society. (527)

If Nwapa could at least accept that “a few” of the literary artists have “tried” to present an objective image of women using only two creative texts to draw her conclusion, then it must follow that

with more texts and thorough analysis and examination, one could bring the complex and objective image of womanbeing in Nigerian literature to more limelight.

Of course, the image of womanbeing featured in Nigerian literature can be viewed as representative of the realities of gender relations in Nigeria. No doubt, the image of womanbeing as represented in some male-authored Nigerian texts is very complex. This is because, as most women would agree, the feminine folk herself is complex, and her nature is hardly knowable. D.U. Opata highlights the complex nature of women in his “Igbo Attitude to Women: A Study of a Proverb”:

... a woman (married) has many bundles. The day she is going to live with her husband, she begins to drop these bundles one after the other right from her parental home, along the way and right up to her matrimonial home. Throughout her married life, she is continually going back to bring these bundles, and never knows what each bundle contains until it is untied. Worse still, the farther away each bundle is from her matrimonial home, the more unpredictable would be the contents of such a bundle (105).

That the nature of womanbeing is unknowable does not in any way mean that she is the embodiment of evil. In Igbo worldview, the concept of dualism pervades, and this is equally applicable to women. This concept means that the attractive can embody the destructive and the dreadful, hence the creation of a sense of tension. The complex nature of womanbeing is further highlighted in Azuonye’s “Power, Marginality and Womanbeing in Igbo Oral Narratives”:

Clearly, there is dualism, paradox, ambivalence and even contradiction in the representation of womanbeing in the Igbo oral narratives...Both feminism and femininity rooted in what appears to be an age-old matriarchal

foundation, seem deeply entrenched in these cultural representations and yet seem oddly enough to co-exist harmoniously with the equally entrenched forces of male chauvinism and patriarchy. (25-26)

This concept of dualism which pervades Igbo worldview can be illustrated using many African texts. In Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, for instance, Agbala is an oracle, a spiritual force beyond human strength and comprehension. In its presence Okonkwo trembles in fear. Agbala is also the name given to a man without a title and the brave Okonkwo despises such a man.

The influence of Western education is indeed having a disastrous impact on the psyche of African intellection. Bernth Lindfors was right when he submits in his "Politics, Culture and Literary Form" that the "legacy of colonialism was cultural confusion" (25). Most modern Nigerian literary critic, who is under the influence of Western education tends to criticize the Nigerian/African culture without fully grasping it. Feminism seeks to re-position the African woman to a "better" way of living, exploring issues like the brutality of polygamy and the preferential treatment given to male children as against their female counterpart. This so-called repositioning of the female folk, as proponents of feminism would have us believe, could undoubtedly develop her into an "independent" being. Such independence, however, could ruin her as it works clearly in opposition to the African concept of sharing and communal living which bounds the African woman to the African tradition.

Womanbeing and Divinity in Nigerian Culture and Literature

In Nigerian traditional culture, women occupy a very attractive position. In addition to the power that motherhood confers on her, she is also linked with divinity, hence her connection with mystery. Azuonye explains this matter further:

In her connections with birth, fertility, sustenance and death as a gateway to the reborn, life after life, to continue the eternal cycle existence, the Igbo earth goddess, Ala, like her counterparts in many other mythological traditions, is represented as a woman. She is not only the mother-goddess that nurtures all creation, she is also seen as the source and custodian of the sacred laws of communal co-existence known as Omenala (literally, that which is done in the land or on the earth) which holds humans together in society and regulate their relationships with the higher supernatural powers.

(4)

As Azuonye has shown, the very idea of an all-powerful mother-goddess who nurtures all creations is not only deeply embedded in the African perception of the human reality but is also universal. In Igbo pantheon, *Ala* is not merely one of the major deities but also the supreme god of Igbo traditional religion. As Azuonye, further highlighted, before the emergence of the male sky-dwelling god, *Chukwu*, presently regarded as the supreme god of the Igbo, Ala, an all-powerful mother-goddess who nurtures all creations is represented as a woman. This is a further explanation from Azuonye in his “Power and Powerlessness of Women in West African Orality” still on gender relationship in Igbo mythology:

The Igbo creator is a twin-deity, Chi na Eke, which comprises of a male principle, *Chi* (Divine power of life) and a female principle, *Eke* (Divine power of creation) ... This is one of the key Igbo mythical formulations of the co-equality and co-evality of the and female principles of life. The life-giving power of Chi is nothing without the creating power of Eke, nor would Eke create anything without the life-giving power of Chi. (9)

The logic in the Igbo mythology above is glaringly obvious: it takes the male and female to create a new life; non can create a new life without the support of the other. In other words, their roles are purely complementary. Even now, arguments from contemporary biology supports it. The implication for this research is that gender in Igbo mythology is complementary. The relationship is just as Azuonye has written: “men and women are neither equal nor unequal” (10).

It is only with this understanding that the negritude trend of African literature in the 1950s and 1960s can be made more comprehensive. Africa was adored as the Supreme Mother Africa or Mama Africa. Below is an extract from Christopher Okigbo’s seminal poem “Idoto” (in Donatus Nwoga’s *West African Verse*) which is very deeply rooted in Igbo mythology and personal spiritual exploration:

BEFORE YOU, mother Idoto,
Naked I stand,
Before your watery presence,
A prodigal.
Leaning on an oil bean
Lost in a legend...
Under your power wait I on barefoot,
Watchman for the watchword at
HEAVENSGATE;
Out of the Depths my cry,
Give ear and hearken. (50)

Like Okonkwo’s unspoken reverence to Chiolu in Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart*, Okigbo’s submissiveness to Mother Idoto is obvious in the poem, and needs not be read twice before it can

be clearly understood. The tone of voice and the words speak for themselves. The trembling captured by his diction.

Womanbeing and Dualism in Nigerian Literature

At a first thought it might be difficult to comprehend the concept of dualism in Igbo worldview, especially by one who is not educated in the African culture and tradition. Is it possible for the adored and attractive to combine with the dreadful and the destructive? Is it possible for the woman who is seen as a life-giver to inflict destruction on man? Why is womanbeing which is associated with divinity also a source of tension to man? This has elicited several critical responses from African critics. Here is Damian Opatá attempting an explanation of the concept of dualism as it applies to womanbeing in his “Igbo Attitude to Women: A Study of a Proverb”:

As we have seen, woman can kill. Because she is mysterious, unknowable to man, she elicits dread. Man, therefore, constantly seeks to define his relationship with her in order to avoid death. Thirdly, and closely related to the mysterious and unknowable nature of woman, is the ambiguous nature of woman. (106)

Equally on this subject of womanbeing and dualism, here is Chukwuma Azuonye’s submission in his “Power and Powerlessness of Women in West African Orality”:

One is to relate it to dualism in Igbo culture, which upholds the possibility that the culture idealises gender relations in terms of the balance of equal and opposite forces, with each sex playing certain powerful roles in the society determined not in terms of equality or inequality as it exists in western cultures but in terms of what may be described as gender capacitance... The other possible parameter for resolving the paradox {} examined is to see the contrasts in terms of contradictions arising from the

traumatic imposition of western values through colonials on a culture in which gender relations were differently organized. (26-27)

Gender Balance and Feminism in Nigerian Literary Criticism

Many female African literary critics who are feminists, particularly those who have acquired education in African culture, are beginning to re-examine and embrace the facts of gender relations in Africa. Some have commenced the process of gradual disentanglement of themselves from Western concept of feminism. First, Buchi Emecheta labels herself an “ordinary writer” in her “Feminism with a Small ‘f!’”, an ordinary writer in the sense of distancing herself from the agitations of feminist ideals. She writes herself out, and further says that:

Being a woman, an African born, I see things through the African woman’s eyes. I chronicle the little happenings in the lives of the African I know. I did not know that by {writing} I was going to be called a feminist. But if I am now a feminist then I am an African feminist with a small f. (551)

A powerful statement made by implication by Emecheta in the above submission is that she neither set out to be a feminist in the first instance nor did she intend to achieve one by means of her creative writings. In other words, she does not regard herself as a feminist; and that if, by any association, she is seen as one, she would rather prefer to be an insignificant one portrayed in her choice of a small letter ‘f’. It is also worthy to highlight that Emecheta wishes to be really vocal about regarding this choice that she has made, hence her unusual decision to insert an exclamation mark in the title of her article.

Besides denying association with feminism as a word with its Western denotations, others have gone ahead to suggest a complete overhaul of the concept by suggesting a change in its name,

perhaps to mark the African feminine agitation off from the Western propositions of feminism which is often combative in its approach. Here is Molaria Ogundipe-Leslie in her “Stiwanism: Feminism in an African Context”:

I have since advocated the word “Stiwanism” instead of feminism, to bypass the combative discourses that ensue whenever one raises the issue of feminism in Africa. The creation of the new word is to deflect energies from constantly having to respond to charges of imitating western feminism and in this way, conserve those energies to avoid being distracted from the real issue of the conditions of women in Africa... The word “feminism” itself seems to be a kind of red rag to the bull of African men. (549)

What is missing in Ogundipe-Leslie’s submission above is the real reason for the charge of imitating western feminism. In the first instance, why do those charges arise in Africa? And if she genuinely believes in the rightfulness of the course that she pursues in feminism, why would she suggest a change in the name? Is it not unreasonable to think that African men do not like the concept of feminism merely because of its name? Of course, what attracts the attention “of the bull of African men” is not merely the name, but what it hopes to dislodge in the African cultural space. If, according to her, ‘Stiwanism’ means “Social Transformation Including Women in Africa”, does it in any way detract from the goals of Western feminism? And if a change in name does not result in a change in ideals of the concept, does she think that “the bull of African men” will remain silent and not raise those charges anymore? Perhaps, one fact that she lacks the courage to admit, like Buchi Emecheta, is disassociation with feminism.

Possibly, the challenge of women which necessitates the combative, feminist approach to realities in Africa is the inability to fully comprehend and embrace women’s revered place in the scheme

of things in African culture. This comprehension is important in African women's definition of themselves. Ogunjipe-Leslie, who had earlier suggested a change of name from feminism to 'Stiwanism' is quoted in Carol Davies' "Some Notes on African Feminism" as saying that:

The sixth mountain on the woman's back – herself – is the most important. Women are shackled by their own negative self-image, by centuries of the interiorization of the ideologies of patriarchy and gender hierarchy. Her own reactions to objective problems therefore are often self-deafening and self-crippling. She reacts with fear, depending complexes and attitudes to please and cajole. (562)

But the question that arises from Ogunjipe-Leslie's submissions above is: If "women are shackled by their own negative self-image", then who is to blame? Is it the African male writers who excluded them from cultural events? Where were the women when the men were busy formulating "the ideologies of patriarchy and gender hierarchy"? Until these important questions receive the attention that they deserve, and answers sought, feminism will continue to be a red flag in Africa's cultural space.

Perhaps, it needs to be said at this time that the portrayal of womanbeing in Nigerian literature became problematic and controversial, particularly in contemporary setting, because radical feminism advocates radical, new rules for female participation in the new Nigerian dispensation, the compatibility or otherwise of the rules with the Nigerian cultural space notwithstanding.

Alternative Approach to Feminist Quests in Nigeria

As has been shown earlier, the African woman was and ought to be satisfied with her place in the African cultural dispensation. The representation of womanbeing in Nigerian literary setting became problematic because radical feminism fashioned out fresh rules for female participation in

the modern African culture. These rules are problematic because the task of reasserting the modern African woman's presence was left to African women who were thoroughly immersed in Western education; in other words, those who lacked roots in African pre-colonial cultures or traditional norms were left with the huge responsibility of reasserting the modern African woman using foreign tools. They deploy foreign analytical tools in the critiquing of Nigerian literary works, setting parameters that are based on what they imbibed from the West rather than the reality of the African context. Found within the African cultural context, they straddle between two cultures of Africa and Europe, and, of course, that implies the presence of an African culture or worldview that is truly insignificant.

The Nigerian woman must first immerse herself in her culture so that her beauty can be acknowledged by her before any agitation for self-assertion. Feminism within the Nigeria literary space claims sensitivity to the conditions and issues that are important to the contemporary Nigerian woman when, in truth, it does not go beyond the surface in its exploration of the Nigerian woman's life and literature. For this obvious reason, it trumpets her "disadvantaged" position without firstly acknowledging and embracing her beauty. And the resultant effect becomes the projection of a misleading view, which in turn makes it difficult for the initiation of authentic analytical frameworks to advance research and creativity on the very privileged and attractive position occupied by the Nigerian woman. If ever the Nigerian woman's voice was silent, as feminism, would have us believe, it can be argued that it was as a result of the huge wounds that colonialism, slavery and inauthentic intellection inflicted on the psyche and life of the Nigerian woman. This is because her voice was clearly heard – even revered- within the societal frameworks that have women's participation as an indispensable part of cultural practices.

Anthonia Kalu in her “Women in African Literature” quotes a 19th century African-American missionary, Amanda Berry Smith, whose report on the African women presents the major issues that feminism in Nigeria grapples with:

The poor women of Africa... have a hard time. As a rule, they have all the hard work to do. They have to cut and carry all the wood, carry all the water on their heads, plant all the rice. The men and boys cut and burn the bush, with the help of the women; but sowing the rice and planting the cassava, the women have to do. You will often see a great, big man walking ahead, with nothing in his hand but a cutlass ... and a woman, his wife, coming behind with a great big child on her back and a load on her head. No matter how tired she is, her lord would not think of bringing her a jar of water to cook his supper with, or of beating the rice; no, she must do that. A great big boy would not bring water for his mother; he would say: ‘Boy no tote water; that be woman’s work.’ (563)

Apart from the obvious sarcasm implied by the deliberate use of expressions such as “a great big man”, “a great big boy” and “her lord”, Amanda Berry displays ignorance of the African culture with a little touch of arrogance. And because her research was subjective, she not only fails to explain why the man moves ahead of his wife with a cutlass, but also where the women went to when the “rule” for all the hard work to be done by them was made. The fact that Okonkwo picks up his cutlass and walks ahead of Chielo and Ezinma in Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart* purely for protective reasons gives us a little clue of what Amanda Berry was attempting to explain but could not because of her bias and subjectivity.

In African culture, a man spends nearly his entire lifetime protecting and pleasing his wife (or wives), on whom childbearing endows with the power of motherhood. He voluntarily becomes unaware of his own plight. Should he hesitate to risk his life on behalf of his wife, ridicule from age mates and his entire community becomes his own lot; in fact, in African traditional society, a man proves his manhood largely by how protective he is to his family members, particularly his wife.

Very early on in Amos Tutuola's *The Palm-wine Drinkard*, the main character transforms himself into a lizard to discover the secret of restoring the voice of the beautiful woman who had chosen to marry "the Skull as a complete gentleman" (25-26). The relationship between Chielo and Okonkwo also demonstrates this fact. Chielo races with the sick Ezinma on her back, calling out greetings to notable community personages. Her action suggests confidence and reliance on a culture that is protective of her. Although Okonkwo is presented as a fearless character, he is cautious of entering Chielo's spaces and runs after her on a second thought, but not without arming himself with his cutlass, only to wait in the shadow for Chielo to reinvigorate Ezimma's health and continuance.

Earlier on in this work, mention was made of Chukwuma Helen and Chima Igbokwe who had alleged in their submissions that in the subjugation of the African woman, that the African men enjoyed the full backing of the African culture, as if women were alienated from the cultural setting. However, it is worthy to note that the facts on the ground with respect to the African traditional setting show that women are never exempted from the cultural process; in fact, they are active participants. The woman-as-mother is a primary narrator to the children. She teaches the children about the society's ways of knowing because she is familiar with it. She symbolizes the essential development and maintenance of the community. Most African female writers are not

oblivious of this fact. Here is Flora Nwapa in her “Women and Creative Writing in Africa” shedding more light on another very important role assigned to women by the very same culture that feminists would have us believe it supported the subjugation of women:

Peace-making is an important function of *Umuada*, *Umunwunyeobu*, and other women’s age-grades. When there is a quarrel between husband and wife, parents and children, these groups of women are called upon to make peace. The role of the wives of the clan is very visible and considerable at home in terms of participating and intervening in their husband’s decision processes. (527)

What is impressive about Nwapa’s submission is that it takes care of all the women in a clan – both those born it (*Umuada*) and those married into it (*Umunwunyeobu*). Nwapa, however, is not a lone voice with regards to this stand. Listen again to Buchi Emecheta in her “Feminism with a Small ‘f!’”:

I am not doing anything particularly clever. I am simply doing what my Big Mother was doing for free about thirty years ago. The only difference is that she told her stories in the moonlight, while I have to bang away at a typewriter I picked from Woolsworth in London (552).

Here, again, Emecheta acknowledges that in the processes of culture in Africa, women were never relegated to the background. In this regard, too, Achebe’s account is not different. In the “Introduction” to *Things Fall Apart*, by Aigboje Higo, this is written about Achebe:

{Achebe} adores his immediate family and cherishes the bonds and responsibilities of the extended family we have in

Nigeria. He has an elder sister of whom he says, ‘She told many of the stories when I was young and I can say it was she who introduced me to the pleasure and art of story-telling.’ (x)

Again, the very important role of women as narrators of the African culture is confirmed in Achebe’s submission. The fact that Buchi Emecheta is “simply doing what {her} Big Mother was doing for free” is also a piece of evidence strong enough to prove that the Big Mother learnt the art of story-telling from her own mothers, too. And the link goes back to time immemorial in the African cultural setting.

Conclusion

Nigerian feminists ought to begin the process of immersing themselves in core African culture to reconsider the trues image of womanbeing in Nigerian cultural dispensation. A realization of the highly exalted position and power that African culture confers on womanbeing would perhaps enable them to wield it more strongly. Western education and its attendant analytical tools should be weighed on the scale of African standards to ascertain its compatibility or otherwise in the context of the African cultural space. A “universal” knowledge without various regional perspectives should be embraced with great caution or even jettisoned, else it would amount to intellectual colonialism.

Already, Carole Davies had, in “Some Notes on African Feminism” highlighted the major flaws associated with a “universal” concept of feminism which our Nigerian feminists champion with all their might:

The failure of Western feminists to deal with issues that directly affect black women and their tendency to sensationalise others create antagonism as

does the fact that white women are often partners in the oppression of both African women and men (South Africa as the most example). The term “Feminism” often has to be qualified when used by most African and other Third World women. The race class and cultural allegiances that are brought to its consideration cause the most conflict. (564)

The chasm that exists between the Western worldview and African culture is clearly highlighted in Davies’ postulations above. Nigerian literary writers and critics ought to be cautious about such Western ideas and attitudes of feminism. Rather than a subjective and surface reading or analysis of Nigerian literary works, a reading based on the armour-wearing and chivalrous Western inventions, there should be a thorough and in-depth reading of literary texts. The labour of trying to force the square peg of Western feminist agitations in an African round hole ought to be re-examined, and the unbalanced emphasis on universalism, particularly as it relates to feminism, should have its wild petals pruned by feminists of Nigerian descent.

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